

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

NOSİSEPTİV MƏRKƏZİN FOTOSTİMULYASIYA MEXANİZMİ

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MECHANISM OF PHOTOSTIMULATION OF THE NOCICEPTIVE CENTER

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Xülasə

Ağrı emalı mürəkkəb sinir mexanizmlərinə sahibdir. Ağrı hər zaman təmas və ya zədələnmə nəticəsində yaranmır, bəzən neytral mühit amilləri də ağrının modulyasiyasına səbəb ola bilər. Hal hazırda xroniki ağrı, fotofobi nəticəsində formalaşan baş ağrıları, migren və s diqqət mərkəzindədir. Optogenetika və işıqla terapiya istiqamətində aparılan işlər ağrının retina-talamik-kortikal mexanizmlərini təhlil edir. Biz tədqiqat obyektimiz olan 6 aylıq, şinşilla cinsindən olan erkək ada dovşanında ağrı hissəsinin işıq stimulu ilə induksiyasının zamandan asılı təlim modelində mərkəzlərarası assosiasiya yaradaraq elektrofizioloji metod ilə mərkəzlərin bioloji cərəyanlarının aktivliyinin qeydini və elektroensefaloqramın təhlilini apardıq.

Abstract

Pain processing involves complex neural mechanisms. Pain is not always caused by contact or injury, and sometimes neutral environmental factors can also modulate pain. Currently, chronic pain, headaches caused by photophobia, migraines, etc. Are in the spotlight. Studies in optogenetics and light therapy are analyzing the retinal-thalamic-cortical mechanisms of pain. We created an inter-center association in a time-dependent learning model of pain sensation induction by light stimulus in a 6-month-old male chinchilla rabbit, which is our research object, and recorded the activity of biological currents of the centers and analyzed the electroencephalogram using the electrophysiological method.

Açar sözlər: fotostimulyasiya, fototransduksiya, ağrı matrisi, EEG, ağrı.

Keywords: photostimulation, phototransduction, pain matrix, EEG, pain.

We created a time-dependent learning model in which an adult male Chinchilla rabbit, our research subject, could gain individual experience. During training, we successfully implemented the inter-center connection, which is the main goal of training, using 2 discrete stimuli. Photostimulation with a pulse lamp was applied to the retina of the eye, and electrical stimulation was applied to the hind leg muscle. Electroencephalography was used to visually study the formation of temporary connections between the visual and sensorimotor centers of the cerebral cortex. Electrodes were placed on these structures under general anesthesia according to the coordinates of the stereotaxic atlas, and EEG recordings were recorded with a Neuron Spectrum pectrum 5 encephalograph.

The light impulses we apply to the rabbit's eye pass through the cornea and are received by the photoreceptor in the retina, and this process occurs within a very short time frame based on the sequential induction of various biochemical, molecular changes and signals. During the phototransduction process, light energy is received and converted into an electrical impulse by the photopigments within the rods and cones in the retina, which leads to the formation of a visual image in the center. Opsin proteins, which are the main structure of the photopigment, are sensitive to light and are sensitive to different wavelengths of light. Rhodopsin in the rods is involved in the reception of weak light, while cones have different types of opsin proteins that participate in the differentiation of colors and the reception of bright light. Retinal and opsin pigment induce the phototransduction cascade. With the reception of light, the configuration of the retinal changes, which activates

the G-protein (transducin) associated with the pigment. Following this, the phosphodiesterase enzyme is activated. Phosphodiesterase is an enzyme that regulates the level of secondary signaling pathways within the cell, hydrolyzing cyclic nucleotides, causing the termination or attenuation of signal transduction. The action of this enzyme reduces the concentration of cGMP and causes the closure of cGMP-gated ion channels, resulting in hyperpolarization of the cell membrane. [6]

The dorsal horn of the spinal cord is the main center for the transmission and integration of nociceptive signals. Nociceptive information is transmitted from the spinal cord via the spinothalamic tracts to the thalamus and sensory cortex, and also via the brainstem and amygdala to the cingulate cortex and insular cortex. There is no single center for the processing of pain sensation, so the term pain matrix is more accurate. The lateral part of the parabrachial nucleus in the brainstem is involved in the generation of states such as fear, stress, and emotional responses by transmitting information about pain and other unpleasant stimuli to the amygdala and other limbic structures. The PBN not only transmits pain signals, but also modulates their intensity and emotional component, thereby regulating the subjective feeling of pain experience. Nociceptive neurons in the PBN receive input from the dorsal horn of the spinal cord and trigeminal sensory nuclei, and directly from trigeminal ganglion neurons. [5]

Thalamic nuclei are classically considered relay centers for sensory information from the dorsal horn of the spinal cord and brainstem to the cortex. Studies

have revealed that there is multisensory integration between the lateral geniculate nucleus and the ventral posterior nucleus of the thalamus. [4]

The light stimulus is converted into nociceptive signals by the trigeminovascular pathway, which indirectly induces the pain center. The trigeminovascular pathway includes the parts of the trigeminal nerve that innervate the meninges and cerebral vessels. Light directly activates intraocular trigeminal nociceptors, which in turn activate second-order nociceptive neurons in the trigeminal nucleus of the spinal cord, causing pain. Light amplifies pain through the convergence of light signals from the retina and nociceptive signals from the meninges in the same thalamic neurons that project to the somatosensory cortex. The neuronal activity of the nociceptive pathway underlying pain is modulated at the level of the posterior thalamus by direct input from the retina. Light enhances the activity of thalamic trigeminovascular neurons in a manner similar to the activation of melanopsin-expressing RGCs by light, and a portion of the dura mater (the outermost and thickest layer that protects the brain and spinal cord from mechanical shock) thalamic neurons are located in the posterior thalamus. The axons of the light-enhanced dura-sensitive thalamic neurons project to multiple cortical areas, including the primary and secondary somatosensory, motor, retrosplenial, and parietal association cortices. [1, 7]

In the first stage of training, we recorded the bioelectric activity of both centers separately. The bioelectric activity in the visual center was recorded by applying a light stimulus to the retina of the eye, and the bioelectric activity of the centers was recorded by applying a weak electrical stimulus to the leg muscle at 20-second intervals. Time intervals are a very important aspect in training. During the continuity of the 20-second interval electrical stimulus that we applied to the leg muscle, its manifestation in the center will gradually increase, and the animal will learn this time interval after a while. If we can maintain this continuity, then we will see that the center responds at the appropriate time even if the stimulus is not applied. At the beginning of the training, the light applied to the retina of the eye was a neutral stimulus. In the second stage of training, 4 seconds after applying the light stimulus to the retina of the eye, an electrical stimulus was applied to the leg muscle. We continued the training by repeating this process regularly. Our goal here is to both teach the animal the duration of the interval and to create a connection between two different stimuli. From the 5th minute of the training model, after applying a light stimulus to the retina, bioelectric activity was observed in the sensorimotor center, even though we did not apply an electrical stimulus to the leg muscle. Thus, we achieved our goal at the beginning of the training. The intervals between events are no longer an aspect that determines the formation of experience, but rather, the duration of these intervals and the ratios between them are the content and essence of learning itself. A strong version of this view is that temporal relationships between events are constantly and automatically encoded. These temporal relationships can even be inferred from single experiences. [2,3]

The research was conducted on adult male Chinchilla rabbits kept in standard vivarium conditions. In the study, the bioelectric activity of the corresponding centers of the brain was recorded using the electrophysiological method, using the electroencephalography method. The stereotactic method determines the precise localization of the studied brain structures [GQ, SQ]. The stereotactic method is a medical technique that allows for high-precision intervention on a target located in the brain using a three-dimensional coordinate system. Using the stereotactic method, electrodes were implanted into the cranial bone above the frontal sinus of the rabbit. In this method, a special frame was used to keep the head of the research subject stable. First, the head and brain were cleaned of soft tissues, then the implantation of recording and stimulating electrodes was performed under nembutal anesthesia [35-40 mg/kg] in the following structures: GQ [AP=9, L=9, H=2]; SQ [AP=1, L=1, H=1]. Nembutal anesthesia was used first during the electrode implantation surgery. Nembutal slows down the transmission of nerve impulses in the brain by enhancing GABA receptors. This has a calming effect on the central nervous system, causing depression. The indifferent electrode was placed in the bone above the frontal sinus. After performing the indicated manipulations and completing the electrode implantation procedure, a composite-plastic mixture was poured into the complex consisting of electrodes and a rigid frame. After the operation, sulfalene 0.2 ml solution [1%] was injected intramuscularly into the animals to prevent septic complications. In the experiments, the animals were placed freely in the chambers a few days before the experiments in order to adapt to the chamber before electrophysiological studies. Daily EEG recordings were made with the "Neuro Spectrum 5" apparatus. Photostimulation was performed using a pulse lamp. The conditioned stimulus was applied in the form of electrical stimulation to the leg muscle.

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